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Editors

Dr. Prabodh Shirvalkar
Prof. Dr. Suraj A. Pandit

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Explorations in the North-western fringe of Yamuna Plains (District Sonapat, Haryana)

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Abstract: This paper is an initial report of a village-to-village survey of Sonapat District, Haryana. A total number of Three-hundred and nine archaeological sites were documented during the exploration in 2017-2018 and revisited in 2019. Out of them one hundred sixty are new sites which were the first time on an archaeological map. These belong to Proto-Historic to Medieval periods. The purpose of this paper is to know about the history and culture of this region through archaeological evidence.

Key Words: Archaeology, Exploration, Proto-Historic, Harappan, Pottery.

Introduction

The study area lies in the south-eastern part of Haryana (Fig. 1). The area is rich in archaeological remains. The high density of Proto-historical settlements shows that it was the core area of Harappan civilization. The fertile land of Yamuna plains and availability of water might have played an important role in urbanization during the third millennium BCE in this area. The credit for initiating archaeological fieldwork goes to various researchers like Silak Ram (Ram 1972), Suraj Bhan (Bhan 1975), Braham Dutt (Bhan 1975), Surender Singh (Singh 1984), Ashok Kumar (Kumar 1990), Gulab Singh (G. Singh 1990), R.

Dhankhar (Dhankhar 1990), R. C. Thakran (Thakran 1993) (Thakran 2000) and Vinay Kumar (V. Kumar 2008). They carried out explorations in different parts of the district/tehsil area and brought to light some new sites. After that present researchers conducted a village-to-village survey in all four tehsils of district Sonapat, Haryana as a whole.

Drainage System

The area under the present study is under the part of the Yamuna river plain. Due to the poor surface drainage system and abundant paleo-channels, the water table is very high. The general slope of the district is from north to south. The Yamuna river makes a common boundary of about 49 km between the Sonapat district and Uttar Pradesh state.

Western Yamuna Canal

It is the oldest channel in the region. It was renovated in 1335 A.D. by Firoz Shah Tughlaq. The length of the main channel is 86 km. The main branches of the channels are Agra channel, Munak canal, Delhi branch, Bhalaut branch, Jhajjar branch, Sirsa branch, Jind branch, Barwala branch, Hansi-Butana and Rohtak branch (Haryana District Gazetteer Sonapat 1990).

Eastern Yamuna Canal

When the Yamuna River enters the northern plains near Dakpathar village at an elevation of 790 meters (2,590 ft), the Eastern Yamuna Canal begins here and stops at Asan and Hathnikund curves, heading south (Bhan 1972).

Methodology

- 1) Topographic maps were used by the present researchers for conducted an extensive village-to- village survey.
- 2) A GPS handset (Garmin, GPSmap 60CSx) was used to record the correct coordinates of the sites.

- 3) Proper sampling of the pottery and other remains from the surface and exposed sections of the sites were done.
- 4) The available published literature and survey reports including unpublished dissertations and thesis were examined and their data was also included in this study.

Cultural structure of the study area and Terminology

The area under study is very rich in archaeological forums. The terminology of early farming communities in the Sonapat district is very challenging because some elements of the local sequence are poorly defined. The common finding during the course of explorations were pottery.

Early Harappan

The early Harappan pottery has already been chronicled from various excavated settlements like Kalibangan (Indian Archaeological - A Review 1962-63) (Period-I), Sothi (Dikshit 1984), Baror (Sant, et al. 2004-05) all in Rajasthan state, Rakhigarhi (Nath 2000-01) (Period-I), Siswal (Bhan 1972), Banawali (Bisht 1982), Bhirrana-IIA (Rao, et al. 2005-06) and Mitathal (Bhan 1975) all in Haryana state. These sites have a rich variety of shapes and painted designs of pottery, which in turn establish a regular evolution of the art of pot making in early Harappan times. The early Harappan pottery industry of the study area shows all the six Kalibangan fabrics including the technique of surface treatment, shapes and decorative elements in different sites found in the study area. The pottery was basically wheel-made. It was comparatively thin and light fabric, red to pinkish in colour and painted in black. The design elements were basically geometric. The simplest among them included horizontal bands, rows of dots, latticed triangles, fish scales etc. Shapes included the jar with an out-turned rim, basin and dish on the stand, dishes, bowl and vases etc. Only Sixteen sites of this period have been reported in the area under the present study (Fig. 2) such as Baghru, Bajana Kalan, Gangeshar-2, Gharwal-1, Gharwal-3, Halalpur, Khanpur Kalan-1, Moi Hooda-1, Rukhi-1, Silana etc.

Mature Harappan

The cultural phase that follows the Early Harappan in the region is represented by the developed Harappan phase. The sites belonging to this phase are less than the early phase. Eighteen sites have yielded remains of the Mature Harappan period (Fig. 3). Some important sites out of them are such as Banwasa-2, Baroda Mor-2, Bhathotri, Bhawar-2, Chhapra-2, Gangana-2, Gangeshar-2, Gharwal-1, Gharwal-3, Holaheri, Mahmudpur Mazra etc. those have yielded Harappan ceramic as well as other associated remains such as 'S' shaped jars, goblets, perforated jars, dish-on-stand with a long stem, chert blades, cubical weights, beads of semi-precious stones, triangular cakes, etc. Harappan ceramic assemblage mainly belongs to red-ware, made of well-levigated clay, turned on the fast wheel and generally well fired. It is found generally painted in black. The main shapes are goblets, cylindrical perforated jars, vases with out-turned rims, disc-based bowls, dish-on-stand etc.

Late Harappan

The next phase represents the degeneration of the Harappan civilization with regard to civic standards and craft activities. It is the mixture of Early Harappan and Harappan types but on the whole Late Harappan pottery is dominated by the Harappan fabric with some modification of shapes, potting, surface treatment, design and decorations. It is dominantly wheel-made and well-fired red ware. It generally consists of a dull red ware of medium to the sturdy fabric of soft firing technique. Occasionally its exterior tends to peel off giving a look of the decline. During the course of exploration, Seventy-Nine sites have yielded the remains of this phase (Fig. 4). Out of fifty-three sites were occupied for the first time by late Harappan people. Eighteen sites of the late Harappan were occupied by the same place where the Mature Harappan period peoples settled. In absence of excavation, it is difficult to say that there is a cultural break between the Mature Harappans and Late Harappans or overlap. The classical Harappan shapes like goblets, perforated jars and classical Harappan paintings fell out of use but some

shapes such as beakers, nail-headed bowls, dish-on-stands with long stems etc. were continued. Some important sites are Baghru, Bajana Kalan, Banwasa-2, Baroda Mor-2, Baroda Thuthan-2, Barona, Barota-2, Bhathgaon-3, Bhathotri, Bhawar-2, Chhapra-2, Chhatehra-2, Datauli, Gangana-1, Gangeshar-2, Holaheri, Jhinholi, Kailana Khas-2, Kakana, Kasandi-2, Khanpur Kalan-1, Kilorad, Kohla, Naina Tatarpur, Pipli-1, Rajlu Garhi, Rindhana-4, Rukhi-1, Sisana-1etc.

Painted Grey Ware

The fourth group of the ceramic industry is Painted Grey Ware (PGW) and its associated wares. The first time, the Painted Grey Ware was found at Ahichhatra (Ghosh and Panigarhi 1946) and its full significance was realized only after B.B. Lal's excavations at Hastinapur (Lal 1954) in the early fifties. Since then, explorations carried out in different parts of northern India have brought to light about 1000 sites. Its distribution is confirmed in north-eastern Rajasthan, Haryana, Punjab, and the upper Ganga-Yamuna basin in western U.P. The main shapes of this ceramic include bowls, dishes, cups and basins. The pots are painted in black, sometimes in red with simple horizontal bands, vertical and oblique lines, rows of dots as dashes, concentric circles, semi-circles and simple or intersecting loops. This ware is found in association with grey ware and red ware. It was fired in reduced conditions. The course of exploration thirty-two PGW sites were found (Fig. 5). Some of them such as Agwanpur, Ahulana, Balanpur, Baroda Mor-2, Baroda Thuthan-2, Bhawar-1, Chhapra-2, Chhatehra-2, Datauli, Gharwal-3, Kailana Khas-2, Kakana, Khanpur Kalan-1, Kumaspur, Moi Hooda-1, Panchi Gujran, Pipli-1, Rukhi-1, Siwana etc.

Historical

Historical period pottery is partly pale red and greyish with striation marks, whereas the outer surface is pale red. These sherds seem to hint at the lack of requisite control over the firing process and the resultant impact of pottery in terms of shade but most of the sherds are the best

example of this ware and high quality decorated with different patterns. This could also perhaps provide an insight in regard to the nature of the substance used for pre-firing decoration. The colour contrast and brightness of this substance seem to have been subjected to the degree and quality of the firing process. Total Two Hundred thirty-four sites of this period were found (Fig. 6). Some important sites of this phase in the region such as Banwasa-2, Baroda Mor-2, Baroda Thuthan-1, Kasandi-2, Khanpur Kalan-1, Gangeshar-2, Gharwal-3, Mahmudpur Mazra and Moi Hooda-1 were discovered. The number of sites indicated that after 600 BCE the area under the present study was thickly populated as compared to the proto-historic period. Common shapes of historical pottery were represented by bowls with incurved rims, carinated cooking handis, vases, spouted vases, basins, lid and incense burner. In the absence of excavation in the region, it is to emerge a flick picture of the historical period.

Medieval

In the next phase total One Hundred Eighty-Seven sites of the medieval period were explored during the survey (Fig. 7). Some important sites of this region such as Anwali-1, Baroda Mor-2, Baroda Thuthan-1, Chhapra-1, Gharwal-3, Kasandi-1, Khanpur Kalan-1, Moi Hooda-1, Mohana-2 and Saragthal-1 etc. Main shapes include sharp-edged bowls, vases, pots etc. a few sherds of glazed ware were also collected during the explorations.

Discussion

The authors documented a total number of 308 sites those have archaeological importance during the course of exploration. A large number of antiquities were collected, which helped us to reconstruct various aspects of various periods or cultures. These sites range in date from Early Harappan to Medieval times. Most of the sites are now under cultivation or under Modern habitation. Pottery and other associated finds of different cultures were collected from these sites to study for

the different aspects of the cultures. But in addition to this, the effort has been made to also plug the major gap in previous works. Firstly, the earlier researchers have not given various details about the location and size of the sites. Secondly, some of the sites needed systematic investigation, and as a consequence of this, a number of sites have yielded new cultural sequences not reported earlier.

During the course of explorations, the main emphasis was laid on locating the sites and on observing the distribution pattern of cultural remains present on them. The antiquity of sites and chronology of cultural remains found on them have been decided on the basis of the occurrence of well-known and dated ceramic industries of ancient cultures. The estimation of the size of the sites has been made on the basis of the area up to which pottery was found.

Following tables Showing explored sites in Sonapat (Tehsil-wise) along with geo-coordinate, previous research work and cultural sequence.

Gannaur Tehsil

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
1.	Agwanpur	29°06'24.0"	76°59'36.0"	6	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	GW, His (RW), Med.
2.	Ahulana	29°11'44.0"	76°57'38.5"	10	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	LH, PGW.
3.	Atail	29°11'13.0"	76°57'26.0"	2	New	His, Med.
4.	Bajana Khurd	29°09'17.0"	76°52'11.0"	2	R.C. Thakran	His(RW), Med.
5.	Balanpur	29°10'01.0"	76°57'38.0"	2	Silak Ram, Braham Dutt, R.C. Thakran	PGW, His (Kusana), E.Med.
6.	Bali Qutabpur	29°11'42.0"	76°54'41.0"	10	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	His, Med.
7.	Bhadana	29°02'54.3"	77°02'20.5"	3	R.C. Thakran	RW, E.Med.
8.	Bhagan	29°04'07.8"	77°02'46.2"	2	R.C. Thakran	RW, E.Med.
9.	Bhamar	29°08'51.0"	76°56'42.0"	8	Silak Ram 1972, R.C. Thakran 2000.	His (RW), E.Med.
10.	Bhrate	29°05'10.0"	77°00'42.0"	4	New	His, Med.
11.	Bhora rasulpur-1	29°11'06.0"	76°59'14.0"	2	New	His, Med.
12.	Bhora rasulpur-2	29°10'57.0"	76°58'44.0"	2	New	His, Med.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
13.	Chindoli	29°07'45.0"	77°07'02.0"	6	New	His.
14.	Chirsami	29°09'34.0"	77°02'37.0"	3	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	GW, His (RW), E.Med.
15.	Dabarpur	29°07'30.0"	76°53'16.0"	2	New	Med.
16.	Datauli	29°09'39.0"	77°05'01.0"	2	R.C. Thakran	LH, PGW (GW), His (RW, Kusana), Med.
17.	Gannaur	29°07'20.0"	77°01'11.0"	4	R.C. Thakran	His (RW), Med.
18.	Gujjar Kheri	29°09'36.0"	76°58'21.0"	20	R.C. Thakran	His (RW).
19.	Gummar	29°07'50.0"	76°59'33.0"	2	R.C. Thakran	PGW (BSW), His (RW, NBPW).
20.	Jaffarpur-1	29°10'28.0"	76°59'52.0"	2	New	His.
21.	Jaffarpur-2	29°10'09.0"	76°59'42.0"	4	New	His.
22.	Jalalabad	29°09'01.0"	76°59'32.0"	12	New	Med.
23.	Kheri Tega-1	29°07'56.0"	77°04'32.0"	2	New	His.
24.	Kheri Tega-2	29°08'03.7"	77°05'11.6"	3	R.C. Thakran	RW, E.Med.
25.	Khubru	29°09'29.0"	76°56'25.0"	2	New	His, Med.
26.	Machrli	29°07'58.0"	76°58'50.0"	5	New	His.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
27.	Mahmudpur Mazra	29°07'55.0"	76°54'17.0"	10	New	LMH, LH, His.
28.	Panchi Jattan	29°05'20.0"	76°58'44.0"	4	New	His.
29.	Panchi Gujbran	29°09'31.0"	77°00'57.0"	5	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	GW, His (RW), Med.
30.	Pipli Khera	28°06'04.0"	77°03'37.0"	10	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	GW, BSW, His.
31.	Pugthla-1	29°10'59.0"	76°52'12.0"	4	New	His, Med.
32.	Pugthla-2	29°11'49.0"	76°51'52.0"	4	New	His, Med.
33.	Purkhas Rathi	29°08'55.0"	76°56'40.0"	4	New	His, Med.
34.	Rajlu Garhi	29°05'25.0"	77°00'52.0"	10	New	LH, His, Med.
35.	Ram Nagar	29°05'38.0"	77°05'21.0"	2	New	His, Med.
36.	Rasulpur	29°05'49.0"	77°07'36.0"	3	New	His, Med.
37.	Saiya Khera	29°08'12.0"	76°55'33.0"	4	New	His.
38.	Sanpera	29°06'14.0"	77°04'24.0"	5	New	His.
39.	Shatwali	29°06'04.2"	76°55'03.6"	2	New	Med.
40.	Sirdhana	29°10'38.0"	76°54'07.0"	2	New	His, Med.
41.	Tewri	29°09'32.0"	76°53'36.0"	6	Silak Ram	His, Med.
42.	Udespur	29°06'01.0"	76°59'14.0"	2	New	Med.

Gohana Tehsil

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
1.	Ahmadpur Mazra	29°13'33.2"	76°42'00.3"	3	New	Med.
2.	Ahulana-1	29°07'06.6"	76°39'24.9"	3	New	His.
3.	Ahulana-2	29°07'08.0"	76°38'12.4"	2	New	His.
4.	Anwali-1	29°00'06.1"	76°46'59.5"	4	New	Med.
5.	Anwali-2	28°59'54.7"	76°45'27.5"	10	R.C. Thakran	RW, E.Med.
6.	Bajana Kalan	29°09'33.0"	76°50'29.6"	4	New	EH, LH, His, Med.
7.	Bali	29°03'31.9"	76°44'24.6"	3	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran, Vinay Kumar	His (RW), Med.
8.	Banwasa-1	29°08'34.8"	76°33'43.9"	4	New	Med.
9.	Banwasa-2	29°09'16.2"	76°33'44.0"	3	New	LMH, LH, His, Med.
10.	Banwasa-3	29°08'33.0"	76°34'25.7"	15	R.C. Thakran	LH.
11.	Baroda Mor-1	29°09'31.7"	76°35'38.1"	4	New	His, Med.
12.	Baroda Mor-2	29°08'53.7"	76°35'18.3"	6	Gulab Singh, R.C. Thakran	MH, LH, PGW, His (L.Kusana, rang Mehal Type), Med.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
13.	Baroda Thuthan-1	29°08'34.0"	76°37'31.4"	15	R.C. Thakran	LMH, LH, His, Med.
14.	Baroda Thuthan-2	29°07'05.2"	76°37'13.0"	4	R.C. Thakran	EH, MH, LH, PGW.
15.	Barota-1	29°07'19.8"	76°44'12.3"	10	New	Med.
16.	Barota-2	29°07'20.5"	76°44'33.2"	6	R.C. Thakran, Vinay Kumar	LH, OCP, PGW, His (RW), Med
17.	Bhainswal Kalan -1	29°01'59.7"	76°47'01.9"	4	New	Med.
18.	Bhainswal Kalan-2	29°02'16.4"	76°48'04.7"	10	Vinay Kumar	LH, His.
19.	Bhainswal	29°00'55.8"	76°47'00.4"	10	Vinay Kumar	Med.
20.	Bhainswan	29°05'02.7"	76°39'54.0"	2	Vinay Kumar	His.
21.	Bhathotri	29°14'26.3"	76°45'28.0"	10	R.C. Thakran	LMH, LH, His (RW), Med.
22.	Bhawar-1	29°12'11.6"	76°31'21.0"	3	Silak Ram, Ashok Kumar, R.C. Thakran	LH, PGW, His (RW), Med.
23.	Bhawar-2	29°12'28.5"	76°30'13.3"	2	R.C. Thakran	MH, LH, His, Med.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
24.	Bibbilana	29°00'06.1"	76°46'59.5"	15	R.C. Thakran	LH, His (RW), E. Med.
25.	Bichpari-1	29°13'07.4"	76°38'43.0"	2	Gulab Singh, Suraj Bhan, R.C. Thakran	LH.
26.	Bichpari-2	29°12'40.3"	76°39'41.1"	6	New	His.
27.	Bidhal-1	29°04'38.2"	76°48'25.8"	10	Vinay Kumar	His.
28.	Bidhal-2	29°04'02.7"	76°48'22.3"	2	R.C. Thakran	LH, OCP.
29.	Butana	29°12'19.3"	76°34'24.4"	4	Gulab Singh, Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	MH, LH, His, Med.
30.	Busana Kalan	29°14'07.4"	76°44'14.2"	4	R.C. Thakran	LH, PGW.
31.	Chhapra-1	29°07'35.0"	76°33'00.2"	2	New	His, Med.
32.	Chhapra-2	29°07'56.8"	76°32'22.2"	5	Silak Ram, Ashok Kumar, R.C. Thakran	LMH, LH, PG-W(BSW), His (RW, NBPW), Med.
33.	Chhatehra-1	29°14'46.2"	76°42'31.7"	2	New	His, Med.
34.	Chhatehra-2	29°13'56.2"	76°42'29.5"	15	Gulab Singh	LH, OCP, PGW

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
35.	Chichrana	29°04'02.7"	76°38'03.2"	2	New	His, Med.
36.	Dhanana	29°06'39.4"	76°30'34.6"	4	R.C. Thakran	PGW.
37.	Dhurana	29°13'42.3"	76°47'00.1"	3	Silak Ram	His.
38.	Gamri-1	29°08'34.4"	76°46'27.8"	5	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
39.	Gamri-2	29°09'27.6"	76°46'21.0"	5	New	His, Med.
40.	Gangana-1	29°12'19.3"	76°37'23.7"	3	Suraj Bhan, Gulab Singh, R.C. Thakran	LH, His.
41.	Gangana-2	29°14'11.2"	76°37'58.0"	3	R.C. Thakran	MH, LH.
42.	Gangeshar-1	29°11'13.6"	76°40'29.7"	7	R.C. Thakran	LH, PGW (BSW), His, Med.
43.	Gangeshar-2	29°11'56.7"	76°40'44.9"	4	Gulab Singh, R.C. Thakran	EH, MH, LH.
44.	Garhi Srai Num-berdar	29°08'16.5"	76°42'38.4"	7	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
45.	Garhi Ujala Khan	29°08'26.4"	76°43'04.7"	3	Vinay Kumar	Med.
46.	Gharwal-1	29°11'17.8"	76°33'57.3"	6	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	EH, MH, LH, His, Med.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
47.	Gharwal-2	29°09'20.8"	76°31'21.5"	6	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	LMH, LH, His.
48.	Gharwal-3	29°10'09.6"	76°33'08.1"	10	Silak Ram, Ashok Kumar, R.C. Thakran	EH, MH, LH, PG- W(BSW), His, Med.
49.	Giwana-1	28°58'33.0"	76°44'14.0"	3	New	Med.
50.	Giwana-2	28°58'28.0"	76°45'00.0"	4	Vinay Kumar	His.
51.	Gudha	29°07'26.2"	76°40'41.5"	15	New	His, Med.
52.	Isapur Kheri	29°12'42.9"	76°35'50.3"	5	Gulab Singh, R.C. Thakran	LH, GW.
53.	Jagsi-1	29°12'45.9"	76°39'43.8"	4	R.C. Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.
54.	Jagsi-2	29°12'17.0"	76°39'14.5"	5	New	LH, His.
55.	Jauli-1	29°06'16.3"	76°48'06.5"	2	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
56.	Jauli-2	29°05'38.2"	76°48'00.9"	3	Vinay Kumar	Med.
57.	Jawahara-1	29°15'35.8"	76°47'21.3"	3	R.C. Thakran	LH, PGW, His.
58.	Jawahara-2	29°15'11.0"	76°47'50.6"	3	R.C. Thakran ⁹	His (RW).
59.	Kailana Khas-1	29°10'37.3"	76°46'21.4"	4	New	His, Med.
60.	Kailana Khas-2	29°10'11.6"	76°45'53.7"	6	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran Vinay Kumar	EH, LH, GW, His (RW), E. Med.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
61.	Kakana	29°08'13.5"	76°48'38.8"	10	Ramdhan Dhankar, R.C. Thakran Vinay Kumar	LH, PGW, His (RW), Med.
62.	Kasanda	29°08'06.5"	76°49'54.6"	3	Vinay Kumar	Med.
63.	Kasandi-1	29°08'58.3"	76°50'23.3"	5	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
64.	Kasandi-2	29°08'41.7"	76°50'53.0"	10	R.C. Thakran	LH, Med.
65.	Kathura-1	29°05'31.2"	76°33'21.2"	4	New	His.
66.	Kathura-2	29°05'00.3"	76°35'36.6"	3	R.C. Thakran	MH, LH.
67.	Kathura-3	29°04'44.6"	76°36'07.0"	3	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	His (RW).
68.	Katwal	29°02'35.5"	76°45'19.4"	2	Vinay Kumar 2008	Med.
69.	Kehipa-1	29°07'31.8"	76°34'07.6"	5	New	LH, His, Med.
70.	Kehipa-2	29°07'11.6"	76°35'00.7"	10	R.C. Thakran	LH.
71.	Khandrai	29°09'00.7"	76°41'03.5"	8	R.C. Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.
72.	Khanpur Kalan-1	29°10'05.3"	76°48'17.2"	12	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran Vinay Kumar	HW, EH, LH, PGW, His (RW, NBPW), Med.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
73.	Khanpur Kalan-2	29°09'51.4"	76°49'39.7"	5	New	LH, His (Kusana), Med.
74.	Khanpur Khurd	29°08'15.9"	76°42'08.8"	2	New	His, Med.
75.	Kheri Damkan-1	29°05'48.9"	76°45'27.1"	4	Vinay Kumar	PGW, His, Med.
76.	Kheri Damkan-2	29°05'50.1"	76°46'19.4"	4	Vinay Kumar	LH, His.
77.	Kohla	29°11'17.8"	76°33'57.4"	5	Gulab Singh	LH, GW, His.
78.	Lath	29°05'02.1"	76°46'23.8"	4	Vinay Kumar	His.
79.	Madina	29°05'31.9"	76°39'41.8"	5	New	His, Med.
80.	Mahra	29°05'44.5"	76°40'52.2"	6	R.C. Thakran, Vinay Kumar	LH, His, Med.
81.	Matand	29°15'15.7"	76°42'07.4"	4	New	His, Med.
82.	Mehmudpar-1	29°10'30.7"	76°43'51.1"	6	New	His, Med.
83.	Mehmudpar-2	29°10'58.1"	76°43'16.6"	5	New	His, Med.
84.	Mehmudpur-3	29°11'55.4"	76°41'21.5"	4	Gulab Singh, R.C. Thakran	His (RW) E.Med.
85.	Moi Hooda-1	29°01'28.1"	76°43'38.4"	4	Vinay Kumar	EH, PGW, His, Med.
86.	Moi Hooda-2	29°03'01.9"	76°43'16.5"	3	Vinay Kumar	Med.
87.	Moi Hooda-3	29°02'23.5"	76°43'14.0"	2	Vinay Kumar	Med.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
88.	Mundlana-1	29°11'33.4"	76°45'35.1"	4	New	His, Med.
89.	Mundlana-2	29°13'49.8"	76°45'25.2"	4	R.C. Thakra	His, Med.
90.	Nagar	29°07'34.1"	76°43'31.0"		Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
91.	Nait-1	29°07'03.2"	76°46'43.1"	4	Ramdhan Dhankar, Vinay Kumar	LH, His, Med.
92.	Nait-2	29°07'13.8"	76°46'55.9"	2	Vinay Kumar	Med.
93.	Nizampur	29°13'45.8"	76°30'28.4"	4	New	His, Med.
94.	Nuran Khera	29°11'32.4"	76°35'49.0"	3	Silak Ram, Braham Dutt, R.C. Thakran	LH, PGW(BSW), His, Med.
95.	Puthi-1	29°03'40.4"	76°41'57.6"		New	Med.
96.	Puthi-2	29°03'36.1"	76°43'10.0"	2	Ramdhan Dhankar, Vinay Kumar	LH, GW, His, Med.
97.	Rabhra	29°04'07.9"	76°43'08.2"	3	Vinay Kumar	His, Med.
98.	Rana Kheri	29°16'28.2"	76°36'42.9"	4	New	Med.
99.	Rindhana-1	29°08'46.2"	76°31'04.5"	4	New	His, Med.
100	Rindhana-2	29°07'16.6"	76°30'02.5"	2	R.C. Thakran	PGW.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
101	Rindhana-3	29°08'00.3"	76°31'35.3"	2	R.C. Thakran	LH.
102	Rindhana-4	29°08'38.6"	76°31'03.0"	4	Silak Ram, Ashok Kumar, R.C. Thakran	EH, MH, LH.
103	Rindhana-5	29°09'27.5"	76°31'11.9"	6	Ashok Kumar, R.C. Thakran	EH, LH.
104	Rukhi-1	29°03'24.8"	76°39'55.3"	6	Suraj Bhan, R.C. Thakran, Vinay Kumar	EH, LH, PGW.
105	Rukhi-2(Thakran 2000)	29°02'54.0"	76°40'29.1"	6	R.C. Thakran, Vinay Kumar	EH, LH, PGW.
106	Saragthal-1	29°07'19.7"	76°50'15.7"	3	New	His, Med.
107	Saragthal-2	29°06'51.8"	76°50'06.0"	10	R.C. Thakran, Vinay Kumar	LH, GW, His, Med.
108	Sikanderpur Mazra	29°06'15.3"	76°44'06.5"	2	New	His, Med.
109	Siwana Mal-1	29°15'27.9"	76°35'28.3"	6	R.C. Thakran	LH, GW, His (RW).
110	Siwana Mal-2	29°14'31.0"	76°34'35.7"	3	Gulab Singh, R.C. Thakran	PGW, His (RW).

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
111	Siwanka	29°12'21.5"	76°41'32.7"	6	New	His.
112	Shyamri-1	29°11'58.6"	76°49'40.8"	20	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	LH, OCP, GW, His (RW), Med.
113	Shyamri-2	29°11'16.0"	76°47'29.2"	6	New	LH, His, Med.
114	Thaska	29°06'55.6"	76°40'28.7"	10	New	LMH, LH, His.
115	Tihar	29°02'11.5"	76°49'27.1"	2	New	His.

Kharkhoda Tehsil

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
1.	Anandpur-1	28°54'58.0"	76°56'14.0"	2	New	Med.
2.	Anandpur-2	28°54'42.0"	76°56'28.0"	8	New	His, Med.
3.	Barona	28°50'56.1"	76°54'24.7"	10	Silak Ram	LH, His, Med.
4.	Chhinoli	28°53'00.0"	76°53'40.0"	6	New	His, Med.
5.	Cholka	28°54'27.0"	76°53'13.0"	3	New	His.
6.	Farmana	28°59'40.0"	76°49'19.0"	8	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	EH, LH, PGW (BSW), His.
7.	Firojpur Bangar	28°49'42.0"	76°58'53.0"	4	New	Med.
8.	Gopalpur	28°49'50.0"	76°55'19.0"	3	New	His, Med.
9.	Gorar	28°56'42.0"	76°47'43.0"	10	New	Med.
10.	Jasrana	28°58'44.0"	76°45'56.0"	3	R.C. Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.
11.	Jharonhi	28°55'50.0"	76°56'54.0"	8	New	His, Med.
12.	Kanwali	28°54'10.0"	76°57'15.0"	4	New	His.
13.	Khurampur	28°49'23.0"	76°52'30.0"	4	New	His.
14.	Kidoli-Pehlادpur	28°47'50.0"	76°54'28.0"	3	New	His.
15.	Kundal	28°50'14.0"	76°57'39.0"	6	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.
16.	Mandora	28°53'36.0"	77°00'13.0"	6	New	His.
17.	Mandori	28°52'43.0"	76°59'28.0"	2	R.C. Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.
18.	Moznagar	28°58'02.7"	76°48'45.6"	4	New	LH, His.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
19.	Nakloi-1	28°58'11.6"	76°52'33.5"	3	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	GW, His (RW).
20.	Nakloi-2	28°57'48.9"	76°53'03.8"	3	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	LH, PGW (BSW), His.
21.	Nirthan	28°57'40.8"	76°53'37.4"	4	Silak Ram	His.
22.	Pipli-1	28°51'36.0"	76°55'43.0"	4	R.C. Thakran	LH, GW, BSW, His.
23.	Pipli-2	28°50'32.2"	76°56'02.6"	6	R.C. Thakran	RW, Kusana, E.Med.
24.	Rampura	28°50'20.0"	76°57'50.0"	2	New	Med.
25.	Redhau	28°57'44.8"	76°50'29.9"	2	New	Med.
26.	Rohna	28°51'22.0"	76°52'59.0"	3	New	His.
27.	Silana	28°57'16.0"	76°50'20.0"	3	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	EH,His.
28.	Sisana-1	28°52'50.0"	76°50'13.0"	4	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	LH, PGW.
29.	Sisana-2	28°53'34.0"	76°52'43.0"	10	R.C. Thakran ⁹	LH, GW.
30.	Sothi	28°49'30.0"	76°55'49.0"	2	New	His, Med.
31.	Thana Kalan-1	28°53'10.0"	76°56'54.0"	3	New	Med.
32.	Thana kalan-2	28°52'51.0"	76°56'14.0"	6	R.C. Thakran	His (RW),E. Med.
33.	Ziaudinpur	28°54'00.0"	76°54'58.0"	10	New	His, Med.

Sonepat Tehsil

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
1.	Aterna	28°53.55.0"	77°08'58.0"	5	New	His, Med.
2.	Aurangabad	28°56.16.0"	77°08'21.0"	5	New	His, Med.
3.	Badkhalsa	28°54.48.6"	77°06'37.6"	2	New	His, Med.
4.	Bahera-1	28°53'09.0"	77°10'40.0"	4	New	His.
5.	Bahera-2	28°52'38.0"	77°11'26.0"	5	New	His, Med.
6.	Baiyanpur	28°57'55.0"	77°00'32.0"	3	New	Med.
7.	Bakhtawarpur	28°59.45.1"	77°00'41.9"	3	New	His, Med.
8.	Barota	28°54'42.0"	77°04'06.0"	10	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	PGW (GW), His (RW, NBPW).
9.	Barwashni-1	28°59'57.0"	76°57'21.0"	4	New	His, Med.
10.	Barwashni-2	29°00'21.9"	76°57'43.2"	6	R.C. Thakran	RW, Kusana, E.Med.
11.	Basaudi	29°00.11.0"	77°08'53.0"	2	New	His.
12.	Baghru	28°59'50.2"	76°56'50.3"	7	Silak Ram, Suraj Bhan, R.C. Thakran	EH, LH, His.
13.	Bhatana Jaffrabad	29°03'54.0"	76°56'22.0"	7	New	His.
14.	Bhatgaon-1	29°00'05.1"	76°53'28.6"	7	R.C. Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
15.	Bhathgaon-2	28°58'53.8"	76°53'42.0"	2	New	His.
16.	Bhathgaon-3	28°59'36.0"	76°54'24.3"	7	R.C. Thakran	LH, OCP, His.
17.	Bindroli-1	28°55'25.0"	77°01'40.0"	3	New	His.
18.	Bindroli-2	28°55'07.0"	77°00'29.0"	2	Silak Ram	His, Med.
19.	Bohla	29°05'03.0"	76°51'20.0"	8	R.C. Thakran	LH, PGW, His.
20.	Chatiya Olia	29°03'55.0"	76°58'53.0"	8	Silak Ram, Braham Dutt, R.C. Thakran	GW, His (RW), Med.
21.	Chhatehra-1	28°54'32.0"	77°02'26.0"	4	New	His.
22.	Chhatehra-2	28°54'10.0"	77°02'11.0"	6	R.C. Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.
23.	Chitana-1	29°03'03.0"	76°56'07.0"	4	New	His, Med.
24.	Chitana-2	29°02'35.0"	76°56'09.0"	4	New	His, Med.
25.	Dahisara	28°51.47.0"	77°11'12.0"	12	New	His.
26.	Dhaturi	29°04.37.0"	77°04'27.0"	2	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	PGW, GW, His (RW).
27.	Dipalpur	28°59.17.0"	77°07'10.0"	3	New	Med.
28.	Dodua	29°05'45.4"	76°49'56.6"	4	R.C. Thakran	LH, GW, His.
29.	Dubheta	29°07'44.5"	76°52'04.0"	4	New	His.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
30.	Firojpur Khadar	28°55'35.8"	77°06'25.3"	6	New	His.
31.	Garh Mirakpur	28°59'30.0"	77°10'13.0"	7	New	His.
32.	Garhi Bala	28°54'43.0"	76°59'43.0"	7	R.C. Thakran	LH, His (RW), E. Med.
33.	Garhi Hakikat	29°01'07.0"	76°53'51.0"	4	New	His, Med.
34.	Garhi Manajat	28°53'39.0"	77°03'23.0"	2	New	His.
35.	Halalpur	28°51'33.0"	76°59'58.0"	3	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	EH, LH, His, Med.
36.	Hansapur	28°54'16.0"	77°09'58.0"	6	New	LH, His.
37.	Hasamabad	28°58'29.0"	77°04'42.0"	4	New	Med.
38.	Harsana Kalan-1	28°56'43.3"	76°59'59.9"	3	R.C. Thakran	His(RW, Kusana).
39.	Harsana Kalan-2	28°57'06.0"	76°59'53.5"	4	R.C. Thakran	RW, Kusana, E.Med.
40.	Harsana Kalan-3	28°56'31.9"	77°00'45.3"	2	R.C. Thakran	LH, PGW.
41.	Harsana Kalan-4	28°56'42.8"	77°00'33.1"	2	R.C. Thakran	RW, Med.
42.	Holaheri	29°01'41.0"	76°55'58.0"	4	New	LMH, LH.
43.	Jajjal	28°58'30.0"	77°09'45.0"	6	New	His.
44.	Jamalpur	28°58'45.0"	76°59'21.5"	2	New	His.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
45.	Janti Kalan	28°51.49.0"	77°09'55.0"	3	New	Med.
46.	Jetheri	28°55'33.0"	77°05'07.0"	3	New	Med.
47.	Jatwara	29°00'26.0"	76°59'00.0"	4	New	His, Med.
48.	Javahri-1	29°01'48.6"	77°00'41.6"	4	R.C. Thakran	PGW, His.
49.	Javahri-2	29°01'17.4"	77°00'44.7"	6	R.C. Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.
50.	Jhinholi	28°50'47.5"	77°00'25.1"	7	R.C. Thakran	LH, His (RW), Med.
51.	Jhundpur	28°56.52.0"	77°11'14.0"	3	New	His, Med.
52.	Joshi Jaat	28°57.54.0"	77°04'27.4"	4	R.C. Thakran	RW, E.Med.
53.	Juan-1	29°03'22.0"	76°53'41.0"	6	New	LH, His.
54.	Juan-2	29°04'06.0"	76°53'41.0"	10	New	His, Med.
55.	Kakroi-1	28°57'38.3"	76°57'30.7"	3	R.C. Thakran	His (RW, Kusana), E. Med.
56.	Kakroi-2	28°57'28.7"	76°58'12.3"	2	New	His.
57.	Kami-1	29°03'25.8"	77°01'31.6"	4	New	His.
58.	Kami-2	29°04'22.2"	77°02'15.8"	3	R.C. Thakran	RW, E.Med.
59.	Khatkar	28°52.25.0"	77°10'19.0"	6	New	His.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
60.	Khewra-1	28°57'53.0"	77°07'24.0"	3	New	His, Med.
61.	Khewra-2	28°57'48.0"	77°07'40.0"	4	New	His, Med.
62.	Kilorad	29°01'38.0"	76°58'30.0"	15	New	LH, His (RW, Gupta).
63.	Kisora	28°59'28.0"	77°05'30.0"	3	New	His.
64.	Krewari	29°02'52.0"	76°54'40.0"	2	New	His, Med.
65.	Kumaspur	29°00'12.0"	77°05'51.0"	7	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	GW, BSW, His (RW, NBPW).
66.	Kurar-1	29°03'07.0"	77°02'28.2"	7	R.C. Thakran	His, E. Med.
67.	Kurar-2	29°02'30.0"	77°01'49.9"	4	New	His, Med.
68.	Ladpur	28°54'55.0"	77°02'13.0"	5	New	Med.
69.	Lehrara-1	28°58'54.0"	77°00'58.0"	4	New	Med.
70.	Lehrara-2	28°58'25.6"	76°59'51.1"	4	Surender Singh, R.C. Thakran	LH.
71.	Lehrara-3	28°58'19.2"	76°59'50.8"	3	R.C. Thakran	GW, RW, E.Med.
72.	Liwaspur-1	28°57'37.0"	77°05'04.0"	4	New	Med.
73.	Liwaspur-2	28°57'44.0"	77°04'56.0"	3	New	His.
74.	Luhari Tibba	29°00'33.7"	76°52'55.7"	2	New	His.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
75.	Machholla	29°02'13.0"	77°07'49.0"	2	New	His, Med.
76.	Mahipur	28°59'03.4"	76°50'24.5"	5	New	His (Kusana).
77.	Mahra	29°04'11.0"	76°56'06.0"	6	New	His.
78.	Malha Mazra	28°53'46.0"	77°02'23.0"	4	New	His.
79.	Mehlana	28°58'25.5"	76°57'07.9"	15	New	His.
80.	Mohana-1	29°01'16.0"	76°50'43.0"	2	New	His.
81.	Mohana-2	29°01'56.0"	76°52'19.0"	4	New	His, Med.
82.	Mohana-3	29°02'17.0"	76°51'02.0"	5	R.C. Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.
83.	Moi	29°07'13.7"	76°53'16.6"	6	R.C. Thakran	His (RW), Med.
84.	Mukimpur	29°00'10.4"	77°07'38.8"	3	New	His, Med.
85.	Mursidpur	28°59'20.1"	77°07'02.9"	5	New	His, Med.
86.	Murthal-1	29°04'01.0"	77°04'59.0"	3	New	His, Med.
87.	Murthal-2	29°02'18.0"	77°05'56.0"	3	R.C. Thakran	His (RW, Kusana), E. Med.
88.	Nahra-1	28°52'34.0"	77°00'57.0"	4	New	His.
89.	Nahra-2	28°52'35.0"	77°00'17.0"	3	New	His.
90.	Nahri-1	28°51'18.7"	77°02'18.3"	10	R.C. Thakran	LH, His (RW, Kusana), Med.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
91.	Nahri-2	28°50'52.7"	77°02'43.0"	5	R.C. Thakran	RW, Kusana, E.Med.
92.	Naina Tatarpur	29°03'58.0"	76°52'25.0"	10	New	LH, His, Med.
93.	Nangal Khurd-1	29°00'53.0"	77°04'38.0"	3	R.C. Thakran	GW, His (RW).
94.	Nangal Khurd-2	29°01'29.0"	77°04'42.0"	3	New	His, Med.
95.	Nasirpur	28°55'54.0"	77°01'15.0"	4	New	His, Med.
96.	Palra	28°59'30.0"	77°09'19.0"	7	New	His.
97.	Pinana	29°03'45.0"	76°49'23.0"	4	New	His, Med.
98.	Pitampura	28°54'24.0"	77°05'31.0"	3	New	His.
99.	Pubsara	28°55'23.0"	77°10'24.0"	3	New	His.
100	Rasoi	28°54'04.0"	77°06'38.0"	2	New	Med.
101	Rathdhana	28°56'59.0"	77°04'00.0"	6	New	His.
102	Reoli	29°00'44.0"	77°03'36.0"	3	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	GW, His (RW, NBPW).
103	Rohat	28°55'57.0"	76°58'16.0"	2	New	Med.
104	Rolad	29°06'11.0"	76°51'48.0"	4	R.C. Thakran	His (RW), Med.
105	Saboli	28°53'32.0"	77°05'36.0"	3	New	Med.
106	Salimsar mazra	28°59'53.6"	76°52'12.5"	4	New	Med.
107	Seoli	28°55'56.0"	77°07'49.0"	6	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	His (RW) E.Med.

Sr. No.	Site Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area (Acr.)	Previous Work	Culture Sequence
108	Sersa	28°52'17.0"	77°09'17.0"	3	New	His, Med.
109	Shahzadpur	29°02'30.0"	76°58'51.0"	3	R.C. Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.
110	Shandal kalan	29°03'43.0"	76°59'20.0"	3	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	His (RW), E. Med.
111	Shandal Khurd	29°03'18.0"	76°58'56.0"	15	Silak Ram, R.C. Thakran	GW, His (RW).
112	Sultanpur	28°58'24.0"	77°02'20.0"	3	New	His, Med.
113	Tajpur	29°04'09.0"	77°06'44.0"	6	R.C. Thakran	His (RW) E.Med.
114	Tharha	29°03'01.1"	77°00'26.7"	6	New	His.
115	Tharu	29°02'01.1"	76°59'17.0"	3	New	His.
116	Tihara Kalan-1	28°58'32.8"	76°55'15.8"	10	New	LH, His (Kusana).
117	Tihara kalan-2	28°59'14.7"	76°55'25.6"	5	New	His.
118	Uldaypur	29°01'39.0"	76°59'21.0"	4	New	Med.

HW= Hakra Ware, EH= Early Harappan, MH=Mature Harappan, LH=Late Harappan, OCP=Occurred Color Pottery, PGW=Painted Grey Ware, His=Historical, E.Med = Early Medieval, Med=Medieval.

Table 2 showing number of sites of different periods

S.no	Period	No of Sites
1	Hakra Ware	01
2	Early Harappan	16
3	Mature Harappan	18
4	Late Harappan	79
5	Painted Grey Ware	32
6	Historical	234
7	Medieval	187

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Fig 1. Showing the study area in sketch

Fig 2. Showing Early Harappan Sites

Fig 3. Showing Mature Harappan Sites

Fig 4. Showing Late Harappan Sites

Fig 5. Showing Painted Grey Ware Sites

Fig 6. Showing Historical Sites

Fig 7. Showing Medieval Sites

Harappan Pottery

PGW Pottery

Historical Pottery

Historical Pottery

Antiquities from the area

Semi-precious stone beads

Coins of different dynasty